

Project Evaluation and Impact Plan

Version 2.1

Deliverable 5.1

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Administrative information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

Project title	Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data
Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger
Project partners	University of Salzburg, Department of Geoinformatics, Austria Trafficon – Traffic Consultants GmbH, Germany Uppsala University, Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering and Built Environment, Sweden Sustainability InnoCenter, Sweden Ecollective, Sweden
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Purpose of the document

The evaluation and impact assessment work package accompanies the whole project in order to gain valid research results that underpin the DyMoN policy recommendations and research publications. The work package activities particularly center on the results of the DyMoN Framework demonstration pilots and the evaluation of the overall impact of the project activities and results. The evaluation plan defines the criteria and indicators of success (quantitative and qualitative) as well as the design of the measurement procedures and methods. This document outlines the planned evaluation for the proof of concept within the DyMoN project. It describes the needed instruments and measurements as well as the timeline for the evaluation. The achieved results and insights stemming from this evaluation plan will inform the impact report of the DyMoN project.

This document relates to other deliverables, namely D2.2a, D3.2, D4.1 D5.2, D5.3 and D6.3, in that it defines the criteria that are going to be evaluated or are described in the other deliverables.

DyMoN Proof of Concept in Salzburg

1 Research questions

The goal of the proof of concept (PoC) demonstration is to demonstrate the behavioural effects of the nudging repository and its situation-aware nudges on mobility behaviour (i.e., choosing modes of sustainable mobility over car use). Therefore, the central research questions are:

1. Are digital nudges effective at changing mobility behaviour (i.e. from individual car use to walking, bicycling or using public transport)?
2. Are situation-aware nudges more effective compared to non-situation-aware nudges (i.e. no situational component involved)?

To answer the first research question, the DyMoN proof of concept will test the developed digital nudges (from the nudging repository, D2.2a) with participants in spring 2023. Effects of behavioural change will be estimated by regular self-reports.

To answer the second research question, one half of the participants will get situation-aware nudges (depending on weather, traffic situation, availability of public transport etc.) that are only sent out when the data indicates a good situational opportunity, the other half will get non-situation-aware nudges (scheduled every day or every other day at a specific time).

If the situation-aware distribution is more effective, then we should observe a greater change in the group that received the *situation-aware nudges*, indicating that the situation-aware group should have more a greater change in sustainable mobility behaviour (i.e. switching from car use to either bicycling, walking, public transport or a combination).

The outline of proof of concept is described in the following (the proof of concept is also described in detail in deliverable 4.1.).

2 Setup of PoC in Salzburg

- **Test area:** Science City Itzling (<https://www.techno-z.at/en/location-and-service/university-and-research/>)
- **Participants:** It is planned that employees in companies located at and students living in the student housing at Science City Itzling **in Salzburg** will take part in the proof of concept demonstration. Target group are people **who are currently often using their car to get to work, but who could be going to work by more sustainable, active modes of transport** for commuting (i.e. walking, bicycling, public transport) and who want to be part of the proof of concept demonstration. These participants will receive nudges (i.e. notifications via a smartphone app) that can be triggered by situational data (e.g. weather). Participants can decide what *kind of sustainable mode of transport* they would be willing to use (*information in user profile*) and can switch between mobility modes if needed. Content of nudge notifications will be adjusted to preferences, for instance, one person might have a bus ticket, but does not feel fit enough to ride a bicycle.
 - In order to answer the second research question, participants will be part of either the experimental or the control group and will be assigned to one of those groups randomly.
- **Test area activities:** Activities accompanying the proof-of-concept demonstration will be held at the Science City Itzling, such as a kick-off event, workshops (e.g. bicycle repairs), a final event as well as other events fostering the community (e.g. active mobility breakfast). This serves to provide a meaningful frame for the proof-of-concept phase; previous results have also shown that a sense of community is important (Luger-Bazinger & Hornung-Prähauser, 2021). All activities are subsumed under “Science City Aktiv Mobil” which is the name of the ‘challenge’ within the test area.
- **Duration:** The proof-of-concept demonstration will have a duration of three months (23rd of March 2023 - 23rd of May 2023).
- **Digital nudges:** A number of digital nudges will be tested within the proof-of-concept phase that stem from the nudging repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620003>). In contrast to the nudging repository in D2.2a, the nudges were translated into German and shortened to fit with the requirements of the app provider Pandocs.
- **App:** Pandocs (<https://www.pandocs.com/en/>), an Austrian app that is built for holistic workplace health promotion (e.g. fitness, mental wellbeing, nutrition) (see Figure 1). The advantage of not using an app specifically for mobility behaviour is that the app offers more content for a broader audience than an app that is, for example, already

geared towards bicycling. In the app, a new category for active mobility will be introduced for the DyMoN PoC.

During the proof of concept, participants will be using this smartphone app. Through the app, they will receive notifications (i.e. “nudges”). Nudges stem from the *nudging repository* (see *deliverable 2.2a*). The data hub (see *deliverable 3.1*) selects and sends the appropriate nudge depending on situational variables (e.g. weather). In addition, participants can indicate via “challenges” in the app when they have not used the car to get to work and earn gamified points for this action (tracking behaviour).

Figure 1. Screenshots from Pandocs app. From left to right: The notifications containing the nudges, The starting screen in the pandocs app with the group “Science City Aktiv Mobil” for the PoC, a list of “challenges”, an example of a “challenge”.

3 Measuring results

3.1 Operationalization of target behaviour

The ideal way to measure target behaviour and consequently, behaviour change, is a combination of different approaches (e.g. self-reports and trajectories from GPS location). However, the more complex the data acquisition and the effort for participants get, the lower the rate of commitment from the participants. In addition, technical restraints (such as constant tracking of geo location via an app) pose further limitations. For sustainable and pro-environmental behaviour, *self-reports* are a common tool, ranging from the use of single items to multi-item scales (see Lange & Dewitte, 2019). In DyMoN, the target behaviour describes the choice of more sustainable modes of transport (as defined in the project by bicycling, walking, public transport) instead of choosing the car. This choice can be operationalized in different ways, for example, number of trips or number of kilometers that were not covered by car use. Within the evaluation, we will operationalize target behaviour from various viewpoints:

- Frequency per week or month that sustainable mobility modes were used.
- Days per week or month that the car was not used for commuting into office, but a more sustainable mode of transport was used.

These operationalizations will be measured via self-reports. This will take the form of a baseline, intermediate and an end measurement via *survey in LimeSurvey* (see [5 Questionnaires used for evaluation](#))

Additionally, gamified challenges that can be filled out within the app by confirming that on this day, a person bicycled, walked, or used public transport for which users will earn points (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Screenshots of the challenges inside of Pandocs

3.2 Behaviour change, attitudes, and values

In order to validly measure an effect of behaviour change, some kind of comparison to a previously established behaviour needs to be made. In DyMoN, we will use a before-after design with a randomization component, which means that we will compare before (baseline measurement) and after measurement of sustainable mobility behaviour (i.e. asking participants at the start, and at the end of the proof of concept about their recent mobility choices). This comparison will be made for both the intervention and the control group that will receive either situation-aware or non-situation-aware nudges.

Behaviour change is influenced by various factors (according to Michie et al. (2011), it is the result of opportunity, motivation and capability that lead to a specific behaviour). Behaviour change is a very complex endeavor and efforts and interventions are not always directly translated into actual behaviour change. Instead, people might change their behaviour at a later point in time, still, it is valuable information what people find helpful within this process. Therefore, individual feedback on the nudges is also collected as well as attitudes, beliefs, and norms regarding mobility (see details in [5 Questionnaires used for evaluation](#)).

4 Evaluation of Pre-Test in Salzburg

Before the actual PoC phase in Salzburg, a selected group of participants will test the set-up of the Pandocs app with push notifications and tracking of behaviour for a duration of two weeks in order to test technical functioning and to make improvements before the PoC in Salzburg. After completing the pre-test, participants are asked to fill out a short online questionnaire via LimeSurvey with the following question groups (see Appendix):

- Push notifications (nudges) within the app
- Tracking behaviour with the app (challenges)
- Open feedback

Feedback for the pre-test will be obtained through the online questionnaire and additionally through personal exchange. Questionnaires follow a similar structure as those for the evaluation of the proof of concept, but are also focused on user experience within the app in order to improve.

5 Data used for evaluation

5.1 Questionnaires

The questionnaires for the proof-of-concept phase in Salzburg follow the design shown in *Figure 3*. There will be a baseline questionnaire (T_0), and a final questionnaire (T_1). Some scales of the questionnaires will be repeated in subsequent questionnaires to allow a before-after comparison. All questionnaires will be administered online via LimeSurvey and will be shown within the Pandocs app.

We will use the following scales within the questionnaires:

- Mobility habits & choices: Mobility habits and choices of participants are assessed for commuting as well as outside work. Scales are taken from similar surveys of mobility (e.g. [HERRY Consult](#), HELIOS & ZGIS Radumfrage 2021).
- Attitudes, beliefs and norms: PsyVKN (Hunecke, Heppner, & Groth, 2022) is used for assessing the psychological characteristics of transport use. PsyVKN presents a theoretically based and empirically validated questionnaire on the psychological determinants of choosing car, public transport, and bicycle transportation. The questionnaire was changed slightly regarding five items to include more sustainable mobility options as the original version is mostly focused on public transport as well as bicycling.

Figure 3. Evaluation design for administration of questionnaires.

5.1 Data from Pandocs app

Some aspects will be evaluated by exported data that gives insights about user behaviour within the Pandocs app. This data will be transferred to Salzburg Research at the end of the proof of concept and will include socio-demographic information about users, challenges that users completed (i.e. tracking of their mobility behaviour) as well as information about when and which users received specific nudges. LimeSurvey (used for questionnaires) includes the user ID (filled in automatically once a user opens the app), so the questionnaire data can be linked to the data from the Pandocs app. In addition, there will be information whether users received a situation-aware or global nudge (see D3.1 “DyMoN Data hub, tools and data processing model”, for in-depth technical discussion of this concept).

6 Evaluation timeline

Pre-test: 31.01.23 bis 16.02.23

Baseline measurement: March / April 2023

Final questionnaire: May 2023

Data export from Pandocs app: May 2023

References

- Hunecke, M., Heppner, H., & Groth, S. (2022). Fragebogen zu psychologischen Einflussfaktoren der Nutzung von Pkw, ÖPNV und Fahrrad (PsyVKN). *Diagnostica*, 68(1), 3–13. doi: 10.1026/0012-1924/A000277.
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Appendix

Questionnaire used in pre-test

DyMoN - Feedback Pre-Test

Dear colleagues, thank you for participating in the pre-test in the DyMon project! By means of the survey we would like to get feedback from you and thus also test the integration in the app - it takes about 5 minutes to fill in. Your feedback is very valuable for us and the further course of the project! We may also come back to you with more questions about your feedback afterwards.

Notifications

This part is about the push notifications you received in the Pandocs app.

How do you rate the frequency with which you received the notifications? Please select only one of the following answers:

- Have received notifications too often
- Frequency was okay for me
- Received notifications too infrequently
- Other: _____

How would you rate the timing of the push notifications? Please select only one of the following answers:

- Timing was mostly appropriate
- Timing was mostly not appropriate
- Other: _____

How appropriate did you find the content of the push notifications for you personally? Please select only one of the following answers:

- I found the content very appropriate for me
- I found the content appropriate
- I found the content less appropriate
- I did not find the content appropriate at all

How motivating did you find the push notifications for your personal mobility behavior?

Please select only one of the following answers:

- Very motivating
- Motivating
- Rather less motivating
- Not motivating
- Other: _____

What content of the push notifications did you particularly like? Please select only one of the following answers:

- Info about current weather / weather forecast
- Info about traffic situation
- Info about environment and mobility behavior
- Info about social aspects and your fellow men
- Info about preparation and planning
- Other: _____

Anything else you'd like to tell us about push notifications? Please enter your answer here:

Handling the app

The following is about how you use the app and record your activities.

How do you rate the recording of your mobility decisions in the Pandocs app? Please select only one of the following answers:

- I understood the recording of mobility behaviour via app immediately.
- It took me a while to understand the recording.
- The recording via the app was unclear to me.
- Other: _____

How often did you record your mobility behavior in the app during the test period? Please select only one of the following answers:

- After every trip to the office
- After almost every trip to the office
- Rarely
- Never
- Other: _____

If you have never or almost never recorded your mobility behavior, what could help you change that? _____

Did you use any other features of the Pandocs app during the test period? Please select all that apply:

- Fitness and workouts
- Meditation and mental training
- Recipes
- No

- Other: _____

Any other experiences or feedback you'd like to share? _____

Thank you for your participation!

Questionnaire used for baseline measurement T(0)

This survey is about your choice of transport on the way to work (the way from home to work and back).

Therefore, please complete this survey on a day when you were at your place of work, i.e. when you were not off work or working in your home office.

The way to work

- *What mode of transportation did you use to get to work today?*
 - On foot
 - Bike or e-bike
 - Public transportation (Bus or train)
 - Moped or motorcycle
 - By car as driver
 - Electric car as driver
 - Car or electric car as passenger
 - Other: _____
- *Is the mode of transport you indicated for today typical for your commute?*
 - Yes, it is typical
 - No it is not typical
- *What other modes of transport do you usually use to get to work?*
 - On foot
 - Bike or e-bike
 - Public transportation (Bus or train)
 - Moped or motorcycle
 - By car as driver
 - Electric car as driver
 - Car or electric car as passenger
 - Other: _____
- *What is the approximate distance (in km) between your home and your place of work (in km)? _____*
 - *How often do you think about what mode of transport you should use to get to work?*
 - Very often
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never

- *To what modes of transport do you have access in general?*
 - Car (owned or in household)
 - Bike or e-bike
 - Public transport: climate pass or annual ticket
- *When you need to go to your workplace, how often do you use a car or electric car (as driver or passenger)?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *[empty field for ID, filled in automatically]*
- *When you need to go to your workplace, how often do you use public transportation?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *When you need to go to your workplace, how often do you go by bike?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *When you need to go to your workplace, how often do you go on foot (the majority of the way, not from the stop / from the main station)?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *In a typical week, how many days are you at your workplace (NOT in home office)?*

- *When you think about a typical week, what is the breakdown of the modes of transportation as a percentage for you? Please fill in the percentages so that they add up to 100%.*
 - On Foot _____
 - By bike _____
 - Public transportation _____
 - Car or electric car (as driver) _____
 - Car or electric car (as passenger) _____
 - Moped or motorcycle _____

- *How important are the following criteria to you for your personal choice of transport to and from work? Please rank them in order of importance, with the most important criterion being at the top.*
 - Independence/flexibility
 - Time savings
 - Monetary savings
 - Comfort
 - Environmental protection
 - Fitness
 - Security
 - Weather
 - Status/image
 - Community/social contacts
- *When you remember the criteria you just ranked, does the importance differ between your way to and from work and trips in your leisure time??*
 - Yes, the importance differs
 - No, the importance stays the same
 - I don't know

Mobility in leisure time

The following questions are about your transportation choices during your free time.

- *How important are the following criteria to you for your personal choice of transport for trips in your leisure time? Please rank them in order of importance, with the most important criterion being at the top.*
 - Independence/flexibility
 - Time savings
 - Monetary savings
 - Comfort
 - Environmental protection
 - Fitness
 - Security
 - Weather
 - Status/image
 - Community/social contacts
- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often do you use a car or an electric car?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often do you use public transportation?*

- Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often do you use the bike?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
 - *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often do you go on foot (the majority of the way, not from the stop / from the main station)?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never

Attitudes and barriers

The following question are about factors that affect your transportation choices.

- *How much do the following statements apply to you?*

	True	<i>Rather True</i>	<i>Partly True</i>	<i>Rather not True</i>	Not True
I feel a personal obligation based on my principles, to use environmentally friendly means of transport on my daily commutes					
I feel obligated to make a contribution to climate protection through the choice of my means of transport.					
People I care about think that instead of using a car I should use environmentally friendly means of transport					
People who are important to me would support me if I use environmentally friendly means of transport for my daily commute means of transport instead of					

a car					
I can do what I want to do using environmentally friendly means of transport					
I can manage my everyday life very well without a car					
For me it is difficult to cover the distances in my everyday life by public transport instead of by car					
If I want to, it's easy for me to use public transportation instead of a car for my daily commute					
My everyday organization requires a high degree of mobility					
I have to be constantly mobile in order to meet my daily obligations					
In cool weather I do not like to ride my bike					
I ride my bike even in bad weather					
I can relax well while cycling					
I like to travel by bike					
In public transport, people come close to me in an unpleasant way					
In public transport my privacy is unpleasantly restricted					
Driving a car means freedom for me					
Driving means fun and passion for me					
Being able to apply my driving skills to driving a car is fun for me					
When I am in the car, I feel safe and protected					
When driving, I appreciate being able to decide for myself which people I want to drive with.					

Giveaway

We are giving away [enter incentive]. If you would like to participate, please leave your email address, participation in the draw is optional.

The data of the survey will not be connected with your email, after the draw the addresses will be deleted.

Your email address (optional): _____

Thank you very much for your participation - don't forget to collect your points in the app!

Final questionnaire T(1)

This survey is about your choice of transport on the way to work (the way from home to work and back).

Therefore, please complete this survey on a day when you were at your place of work, i.e. when you were not off work or working in your home office.

- *To what modes of transport do you have access in general?*
 - Car (owned or in household)
 - Bike or e-bike
 - Public transport: climate pass or annual ticket
- *Over the last two months, how often did you use a car or electric car (as driver or passenger) for your commutes to and from work?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *Over the last two months, how often did you use public transportation for your commutes to and from work?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *Over the last two months, how often did you go by bike for your commutes to and from work?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *Over the last two months, how often did you go on foot (the majority of the way, not from the stop / from the main station) for your commutes to and from work?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *How often do you think about what mode of transport you should use to get to work?*

- Very often
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never
- *[empty field for ID, filled in automatically]*
- *When you think of the last two months, what is the breakdown of the modes of transportation as a percentage for you? Please fill in the percentages so that they add up to 100%.*
 - On Foot _____
 - By bike _____
 - Public transportation _____
 - Car or electric car (as driver) _____
 - Car or electric car (as passenger) _____
 - Moped or motorcycle _____
- *How important are the following criteria to you for your personal choice of transport to and from work? Please rank them in order of importance, with the most important criterion being at the top.*
 - Independence/flexibility
 - Time savings
 - Monetary savings
 - Comfort
 - Environmental protection
 - Fitness
 - Security
 - Weather
 - Status/image
 - Community/social contacts
- *When you remember the criteria you just ranked, does the importance differ between your way to and from work and trips in your leisure time??*
 - Yes, the importance differs
 - No, the importance stays the same
 - I don't know

Mobility in leisure time

The following questions concern your choice of transportation in everyday life

- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often did you use a car or an electric car over the last two months?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often did you use public transportation over the last two months?*
 - Always
 - Often

- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never
- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often did you use the bike over the last two months?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *When you think about your free time (outside of the commute and on weekends), how often did you go on foot (the majority of the way, not from the stop / from the main station) over the last two months?*
 - Always
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Never
- *How important are the following criteria to you for your personal choice of transport for trips in your leisure time? Please rank them in order of importance, with the most important criterion being at the top.*
 - Independence/flexibility
 - Time savings
 - Monetary savings
 - Comfort
 - Environmental protection
 - Fitness
 - Security
 - Weather
 - Status/image
 - Community/social contacts

Science City Aktiv Mobil

The following questions relate to the Science City Aktiv Mobil campaign.

- *How much do the following statements apply to you when you think about the "Science City Aktiv Mobil" campaign, where you used the Pandocs app and received notifications?*
 -

	True	Rather True	Partly True	Rather not True	Not True
The "Science City Aktiv Mobil" campaign has motivated me to think about means of transportation.					

The "Science City Aktiv Mobil" campaign has shown me new sides of environmentally friendly means of transportation.					
Thanks to the "Science City Aktiv Mobil" campaign, I have left the car more often.					
Through the campaign "Science City Aktiv Mobil" I have chosen environmentally friendly means of transport.					
Through the "Science City Aktiv Mobil" campaign, I wanted to use environmentally friendly means of transport.					

- *What content in the notifications you received daily, have motivated you personally to use sustainable modes of transportation?*

	True	<i>Rather True</i>	<i>Partly True</i>	<i>Rather not True</i>	Not True
Information about the current/comming weather					
Information on the environment, climate and mobility behavior					
Information about social aspects and your peers					
Information about fitness and health					
Motivation to persevere					
Inspiration for new ways of looking at transportation (e.g., spending time on the bus for yourself)					

- *To what extent did the individual parts of the Science City Aktiv Mobil motivate you to use sustainable means of transport to get to work?*

	Motivating	<i>Rather motivating</i>	<i>Partly motivating</i>	<i>Rather not motivating</i>	Not motivating

Notifications					
Points and prizes in the app					
Community (Contacts with other participants)					
Events and meetings					

Attitudes and hurdles

The following questions are about factors that affect your transportation choices.

- *How much do the following statements apply to you?*

	True	<i>Rather True</i>	<i>Partly True</i>	<i>Rather not True</i>	Not True
I feel a personal obligation based on my principles, to use environmentally friendly means of transport on my daily commutes					
I feel obligated to make a contribution to climate protection through the choice of my means of transport.					
People I care about think that instead of using a car I should use environmentally friendly means of transport					
People who are important to me would support me if I use environmentally friendly means of transport for my daily commute means of transport instead of a car					
I can do what I want to do using environmentally friendly means of transport					
I can manage my everyday life very well without a car					
For me it is difficult to cover the distances in my everyday life by public transport instead of by car					
If I want to, it's easy for me to use public transportation instead of a car for my daily commute					

My everyday organization requires a high degree of mobility					
I have to be constantly mobile in order to meet my daily obligations					
In cool weather I do not like to ride my bike					
I ride my bike even in bad weather					
I can relax well while cycling					
I like to travel by bike					
In public transport, people come close to me in an unpleasant way					
In public transport my privacy is unpleasantly restricted					
Driving a car means freedom for me					
Driving means fun and passion for me					
Being able to apply my driving skills to driving a car is fun for me					
When I am in the car, I feel safe and protected					
When driving, I appreciate being able to decide for myself which people I want to drive with.					

Survey and Interview Mail

If you would like to participate in a raffle (3 x 20 € Altstadt Salzburg vouchers), in the raffle for the picnic to celebrate the 25,000 points or if you are open for a short interview about your experiences with the Science City Aktiv Mobil campaign, please enter your e-mail address here. You are free to decide what we may contact you for. Otherwise, please click Submit to complete the survey. *Your email address for participation on our give-away (optional):*

- *Your email address:*
- *What may we contact you about using this email address? Please choose from the following options:*
 - *The raffle for "Altstadt Salzburg" vouchers for the completed final questionnaire*
 - *a short interview about your experiences with the Science City Aktiv Mobil campaign*
 - *The raffle for the picnic to celebrate the 25,000 points*

Thank you for your participation - don't forget to collect your points in the Pandocs App!